

Polarographic Reduction of *o*-Benzoyl-Benzoic acid

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The polarographic behaviour of *o*-benzoyl-benzoic acid has been studied in McIlvaine (McI) and Britton-Robinson (BR) buffers of different pH values. The electrode process has been found to be pH-dependent. At lower pH values (<5) the reduction takes place reversibly while at higher pH values (>5) it is irreversible. A tentative mechanism of the electrode process has been suggested.

WAWZONEK¹ *et al.* have reported the $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values of *o*-benzoyl-benzoic acid in 0.1 M HCl-50% dioxan and in tetramethylammoniumiodide-tetramethylammoniumhydroxide-phosphoric acid and 50% dioxan mixtures. However, a polarographic study as a function of pH has remained untouched. With this aim in view, this study has been undertaken.

Experimental

A M/20 stock solution of *o*-benzoyl-benzoic acid was prepared by dissolving 0.2826 g in 25 ml of absolute alcohol. The final polarographic solution was obtained by mixing 1 ml of this solution with appropriate amount of KCl (supporting electrolyte) and gelatin and making it upto 50 ml with respective buffer solution so as to give depolarizer and supporting electrolyte concentration 1 mM and 200 mM respectively. The gelatin concentration was kept 0.002%. The pH of the final solution was measured by a Philips pH meter (model 9404). A manual polarograph (Toshniwal) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal) was used for measuring potential (vs S.C.E.) and current respectively. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent and Co., Chicago, U.S.A.) which had the following characteristics in 0.2 M KCl solution at 1.0 volt vs S.C.E. The polarograms were recorded at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the deoxygenation was done by passing purified nitrogen.

$$h_{\text{corr}} = 40.2 \text{ cm} ; t = 4.2 \text{ sec} ; m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.525 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$$

Results and Discussion

Well-defined single wave is obtained at all the pH values in both McIlvaine (McI) and Britton-Robinson (BR) buffers except for pH 8.0 in McI and pH 7.0 in BR buffer. In these two cases waves appear in two parts. However, the sum of the two parts is equal to the wave heights at other pH values. Since the two parts are unequal the reduction in two steps each involving one electron is ruled out.

Such 'splittings' are often due to some sort of 'sluggish equilibrium' between two or more 'forms' or 'species' of the depolarizer². At all the pH values in both the buffers sum of the wave heights of the two parts where splitting occurs (pH 8 in McI and pH 7 in BR) and the two parts separately vary linearly with $h^{1/2}$ thereby establishing that the electrode process is diffusion controlled throughout.

The number of electrons involved in the reduction process has been determined by mill coulometry using method of De Vries and Kroon³. Results are summarised in Table 1. It is evident that this number can safely be taken as 2.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF *o*-BENZOYL-BENZOIC ACID 1 mM ; KCl 200 mM

Buffer	pH	$-E_{1/2}$ volt vs (S.O.E.)	i_d μ A	Slope mV	n
McI	2.2	0.988	5.310	32.5	2.18
	3.0	0.956	5.310	32.8	2.24
	4.0	0.982	5.310	31.7	2.06
	5.0	1.032	5.304	48.5	1.96
	6.0	1.231	5.310	50.6	2.13
	7.0	1.327	5.040	50.8	2.09
	I step	1.334	3.450	42.0	
	8.0				2.20
	II step	1.524	1.680	80.0	
	BR	2.09	0.893	5.500	30
2.87		0.944	5.504	31	2.23
4.10		0.959	5.440	38	1.96
5.02		1.007	5.568	60	2.29
6.09		1.085	5.504	64	1.89
I step		1.198	3.340	—	—
7.00					
II step		1.337	1.436		
7.96		1.350	5.312	64	2.12
8.95		1.383	5.248	66	2.02
9.91	1.434	5.248	66	2.09	
10.88	1.456	5.184	69	2.18	
11.98	1.486	5.248	74	1.93	

Slope values obtained from log plots record gradual increase with pH (Table 1). Thus reduction is facilitated by increase in hydrogen ion concentrations and becomes increasingly difficult with decreasing hydrogen ion concentration. This is an

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indication that hydrogen ions are involved in reduction of the depolarizer.

Course of the electrode process :

From the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots (Fig. 1) for the waves in McI and BR buffers it is evident that there are two segments in $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots in respect of McI buffer while three segments in respect of BR buffer. From this it follows that the reduction

Fig. 1. Variation of $E_{1/2}$ with pH in different buffers
 I. McIlvaine buffer ;
 II. Britton-Robinson buffer.

process of *o*-benzoyl-benzoic acid at d.m.e. appears to follow two and three courses of reduction in McI and BR buffers respectively. The pH ranges for two courses of electrode process in McI buffer are (i) pH 2.2-4 and (ii) pH 5-8 while in BR buffer these are (i) pH 2.09-4.10 ; (ii) pH 5.02-8 and (iii) pH 8.95-11.98. The number of protons (p) involved in the reduction courses in both the buffers has been calculated⁴⁻⁵ from the ratio of the slopes of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots $\left(= \frac{2.303 p RT}{4nF} \right)$ to the wave-slope $\left(= \frac{2.303 RT}{4nF} \right)$. This gives the value of p equal to 1 and 2 in McI buffer at pH range 2.2-4 and 5-8 respectively while the values of p are 1, 2 and 1 in BR buffer at pH range 2.09-4.1 ; 5.02-8 and 8.95-11.98 respectively.

Since the number of electrons involved in the electrode process throughout the pH range studied is two, the following tentative mechanism can be suggested for the course of the electrode process :

1. McI Buffer :

(i) pH 2.2-4

Thus the reduction of (O) in this range leads to the formation of radical anion (B).

(ii) pH 5-8

Thus the reduction of (O) in this range leads to the formation of alcohol (C).

2. BR buffer :

(i) pH 2.09-4.10

In this range the course of electrode process follows the same course as in McI buffer, pH range (i).

(ii) pH 5.02-8

In this range also the electrode process follows the same course as in McI buffer, pH range (ii).

(iii) In the range of pH 8.95-11.98, the electrode process follows the same course as in the range (ii) producing B.

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